

Neural control of synchronization among coupled hair bundles

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Abstract. The system of efferent neurons has been shown to play an important role in hearing, protecting it from damage and thus maintaining the sensitivity of auditory detection. In this study, we apply direct electrical stimulation of efferent neurons to explore their impact on hair bundle dynamics. Specifically, we aim to determine the impact of efferents on the collective response of coupled hair bundles. *In vivo*, hair bundles of auditory and vestibular epithelia are coupled to each other via otolithic or tectorial membranes. We explore how actuation of the efferent neurons modulates or shapes the active motility of coupled hair bundles. Artificial coupling of hair bundles of the sacculi of the American Bullfrog was achieved by attaching them to mica flakes. The experimental setup allowed optical recording of the hair bundles' position over time, while electrically stimulating the auditory nerve in an *ex vivo* preparation that emulated physiological conditions. We observed that efferent activation impacts the synchronization of hair bundle oscillations, sharpening the frequency spectra among the coupled cells. Additionally, the shape of waveform sent produced different effects and degrees of coupling.

INTRODUCTION

The auditory system is critically important for the survival of many species, as it enables them to communicate, navigate through space, and avoid danger. These features depend upon the ability to extract information from environments with multiple competing streams of information, in addition to exhibiting sufficient sensitivity to detect signals as low as 0 dB [1]. Vertebrates' ability to hear and balance is attributed to specialized cells found in internal sensory organs within the ear [2]. Because of their distinctive stereocilia that protrude from a cuticular plate, these essential functional units that execute the initial stage of detection are referred to as hair cells (HCs) (Fig. 1a).

Thirty to fifty stereocilia that extend from the apical surface of the cell body make up the hair bundle (HB). HCs in the vestibular and auditory systems are remarkable sensory organs that can detect subnanometer mechanical displacements of the HB. Deflection of the stereocilia triggers the opening of mechano-sensitive transduction channels and enables the influx of ionic currents (Fig. 1b) ultimately eliciting spike trains in the innervating afferent neurons [3, 4]. The auditory system further contains an active amplifier, which expends energy to enhance the response to extremely small signals. At the level of the HB, internal adaptation process involving myosin motor activity have been shown to lead to spontaneous oscillations [5]. One of the manifestations of the active process, these oscillations can be modulated by mechanical, electrical, and chemical manipulations and provide a useful probe of the internal mechanics of the bundle.

The efferent neurons provide a protective feedback mechanism, transmitting information from the brain's higher order processing centers back to the sensory epithelium [6, 7]. It has long been accepted that the efferent system helps the auditory system with communication and navigational functions [8, 9]. Furthermore, it was shown that the efferent architecture plays a role in the capacity of an animal to extract a single auditory stream from a complex acoustic environment [10]. Prior studies demonstrated that efferents regulate the sensitivity of the auditory system's detection [11] and shield it from harm caused by noise [12]. Direct experimental measurements furthermore revealed that efferents can inhibit basilar membrane movement elicited by sound. However, despite this extensive experimental evidence of its importance, much still remains unknown regarding the mechanisms by which efferent activity exerts its effects on hearing. In the bullfrog sacculus, prior work has utilized electrophysiological recordings to determine the effects of efferent stimulation on the hair cell soma [13]. The empirical data indicated that efferent activation led to inhibitory effects in a large majority of the hair cells; a few hair cells did, however, show a different trend. Prior work in our laboratory has consistently shown a reduction in mechanical sensitivity of individual hair bundles, indicating an inhibitory role of efferent stimulation [7, 14].

While sensory systems of different species exhibit various morphologies of overlying structures, most systems show some degree and extent of inter-cell coupling. Prior work has shown that efferent activation vastly reduces the mechanical sensitivity of an individual hair bundle. In this work, we extend these studies to explore how actuation of

the efferent neurons modulates or shapes the active motility of coupled HBs. In particular, we aim to determine the role of efferents in controlling the ability of hair cells to synchronize their innate oscillations. We achieved artificial coupling of HBs of the sacculi of the American Bullfrog by attaching them to mica flakes. These flakes are transparent, low-density, adherent and flat, allowing their connection to multiple HBs, with the extent of the array determined by the size of the flake. Thus, the use of artificial coupling allows us to vary the size of the system.

FIGURE 1. (A) Schematic diagram of a HC and the innervating neurons. The cluster of stereocilia at the apical surface comprise the mechanosensitive organelle of a hair cell, the hair bundle. Synaptic contacts are present at the basal pole of the HC corresponding to nerve fiber innervations. (B) Schematic of the transduction process. Stereocilia are inter-connected by tip links, which are mechanically coupled to transduction channels. Upon increase in the tension of the tip link due to deflection, the transduction channel opens, allowing the influx of ions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ex vivo imaging was performed on HCs from dissected sacculi of North American Bullfrogs while preserving their physiological integrity. Spontaneous oscillations of the HB were observed during efferent activation under mechanical coupling. Electrical stimulation was found to impact the HBs active motility, modulating the degree of synchronization, characteristic frequency regime, and amplitude of oscillation.

Frogs of either gender were anesthetized (pentobarbital: 150 mg/kg), pithed, and decapitated following protocols approved by the University of California, Los Angeles Chancellor's Animals Research Committee. Sacculi were excised from the inner ears of the animals and placed in oxygenated artificial perilymph solution (in mM as follows: 110 Na⁺, 2 K⁺, 1.5 Ca²⁺, 113 Cl⁻, 3 D-(+)-glucose, 1 Na⁺ pyruvate, 1 creatine, 5 HEPES). The epithelium was mounted in a two-compartment chamber, emulating the fluid partitioning of the *in vivo* physiological conditions. In this arrangement, apical surfaces were bathed in artificial endolymph (in mM as follows: 2 Na⁺, 118 K⁺, 0.25 Ca²⁺, 118 Cl⁻, 3 D-(+)-glucose, 5 HEPES) and basolateral membranes in perilymph, as depicted in Fig. 2a. In order to allow direct mechanical access to the HBs, the otolithic membrane was carefully removed from the epithelium after an 8 min enzymatic dissociation with 15 g/ml Collagenase IV (Sigma-Aldrich).

Efferent stimulation and artificial mechanical coupling

A solution containing the artificial mica flake membranes was pipetted into the endolymph solution bathing the HBs. Mica flakes were randomly dispersed over the cells, and upon settling, found to adhere to HBs underneath. The transparent artificial membranes allowed for optical imaging of the underlying bundles, thus enabling us to track the active motility of the coupled cells. Within the same field of view, hair cells could be observed that were not connected to the mica, thus providing non-coupled and coupled cells within the same recording, for direct comparison.

We introduced external electrical perturbations through a bipolar suction electrode (A-M Systems). The saccular nerve was pulled into a 0.5-mm-diameter silicon tube (Fig. 2b) which was electrically connected to the positive

terminal of the electrode, while the reference terminal was immersed in the perilymph compartment of the chamber [7]. This technique leads to simultaneous activation of all efferent neurons within the nerve. A linear stimulus isolator (World Precision Instruments A395) provided current to the suction electrode, and stimulus protocols were sent to the isolator via LabView (National Instruments). Altered bundle oscillations were observed immediately upon the onset of efferent stimulus and ceased upon its termination. Stimulus were pulse trains “combs” of 5, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 Hz at 50% duty cycle of 100 μ A intensity, and continuous steps of 25, 50, 75, 100, 150 and 200 μ A. Intervals of no stimulation were left before and after the application of the current to observe the changes introduced by efferent activation.

Data acquisition and processing

Recordings were performed using an upright optical microscope (Olympus BX51WI) with a water-immersion objective (Olympus LUMPlanFL N 60X, NA:1.00) mounted on an optical table (Technical Manufacturing). The setup was constructed inside an acoustically isolated chamber (Industrial Acoustics) to avoid introducing external perturbations to the highly sensitive HCs. Images at a resolution of 108.3 nm/px were recorded with a high speed camera (ORCA-Flash4.0 CMOS) at 400 frames per second (fps).

For each set of experiments, motion of the HBs was tracked according to previously developed image processing methods using custom made MATLAB scripts. The centroid of the HB position was determined from the two-dimensional light intensity profile, in each frame of the recording. Plots of bundle position over time then provided traces of its motion.

FIGURE 2. HCs in the two-compartment chamber emulating the ionic concentrations of the natural fluid environment of the sacculus. The nerves are immersed in perilymph at the bottom compartment, and the HCs in endolymph at the top (a). Bottom view of the preparation, the eighth cranial nerve is left long enough to be inserted into a silicon tube, the perilymph that fills the tube is in contact with the electrode (b).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Consistent with the convention in prior literature, positive displacement in the traces correlates to motion towards the kinocilium and corresponds to channel opening. Prior to further analysis, any slow drift in the trace of HB position, reflecting relaxation of the epithelium in this configuration, was removed. HB traces were divided into three "sections", corresponding to recordings made prior to, during, and after the application of the efferent stimulus, and each segment was analyzed independently. Only traces exhibiting multi-modality in the position distribution of the initial section, as indicated by the Hartigan's dip statistic of more than 0.01 and a corresponding p-value less than 0.001, were considered oscillatory [15]. The level of coupling between cells was assessed by computing the cross correlation between pairs of individual traces and with the mica flake. The correlation coefficient (CC) threshold for coupling was chosen to be 0.2, calculated from several sets of non-coupled saccular cells (distributions of \sim 2000 pairs each); the value of 0.2 was found to be between 4σ and 5σ of the distribution's Gaussian fit. Cells external to the artificial membrane were analyzed as controls. Parameters were extracted from the position traces to describe the effect of efferent activation on the spontaneous oscillation of the cells. The characteristic frequency was determined as the peak of the frequency spectrum of a trace, together with the average of the instantaneous frequency. The

amplitude was defined as half of the the distance between the two local maxima in the distribution position. The mean open probability was obtained by computing the area under the positive position distribution plot, divided by the area under the full probability density function.

Fixed-frequency pulse train efferent stimulation

The current intensity for pulse train stimuli was fixed at $100 \mu\text{A}$ being in the medium range of prior experiments (25 to $200 \mu\text{A}$). For all of the frequencies applied (5 , 20 , 40 , 60 , 80 , 100 Hz), strong phase-locking was observed among all of the cells under the artificial membrane. The degree of synchronization of motion among the cells and mica, quantified by the CC, showed a marked increase upon activation of efferents. Figure 3 and 4 depict the motion of selected coupled and control cells during a pulse train stimulus, together with the corresponding CC and bundle frequency. The amplitude (data not shown) was not found to be strongly affected, even at intensities of the pulse trains found to strongly reduce spontaneous oscillations in individual bundles [7]. A phase-locked response was consistently observed at the onset of efferent stimulation in cells under the artificial membrane, but not observed for every control cell, particularly at higher frequencies (Fig. 4b). Efferent activity hence enhances the synchronization among cells, as the CC for most pairs of cells cross the threshold of 0.2 during the electrical stimulation and return to their original state upon stimulus termination.

FIGURE 3. The spontaneous oscillations phase-locked immediately upon the onset of the efferent stimulus. (a) Spontaneous oscillations before, during, and after efferent modulation (pulse train: 5 Hz, $100 \mu\text{A}$) are displayed for three representative HBs under the artificial membrane (red) and two control cells outside the membrane area (blue). The mica flake motion is presented in black at the top, and at the bottom the shape of the stimulus waveform is depicted. The traces have arbitrary vertical offsets for clarity. The efferent stimulus was in effect for the duration occurring between the gray vertical dashed lines (10 s). (b) CC and bundle characteristic frequency for all the cells in this experiment (gray) before, during, and after efferent stimulation. Highlighted in black (*) are CCs for the pairs of hair bundle traces with the artificial membrane position. Efferent activity pushes the system toward a fully synchronized state, as all the pairs display a CC above the threshold value. Red (*) shows the characteristic frequency for HBs coupled to the mica flake motion, while blue (x) marks the control ones. During activation of efferents, the frequency of all HBs converges to the stimulus frequency, in this case 5 Hz.

Continuous efferent stimulation

A prolonged step stimulus introduces continuous efferent activation through the whole nerve bundle. In this case, there is no introduction of a specific frequency component, and the spontaneous oscillations speed is regulated in a less constrained manner. Efferent activity was found to strongly speed up HB oscillations, while reducing their amplitude of motion, consistent with previous experiments [7, 14]. The experiment corresponding to a $150 \mu\text{A}$ step stimulus is depicted in Fig. 5. For all stimulus intensities, CCs did not exhibit differences in values obtained before, during and after stimulation.

FIGURE 4. (a) Spontaneous oscillations before and during efferent modulation (pulse train: 40 Hz, 100 μ A) are displayed for three representative HBs under the artificial membrane (red) and a control cell outside the membrane area (blue). The mica flake motion is presented in black at the top, and at the bottom the shape of the stimulus is depicted. The traces have arbitrary vertical offsets for clarity. The efferent stimulus commenced at gray vertical dashed line mark. (b) CC and bundle characteristic frequency for all the cells in this experiment (gray) before, during, and after efferent stimulation. Highlighted in black (*) are CCs for the pairs of hair bundle traces with the artificial membrane position. Efferent activity presents a milder effect in the degree of coupling, although an increase in the values of the CC is observed, with pairs of cells crossing the threshold into a synchronized state. Red (*) shows the characteristic frequency for HBs coupled to the mica flake motion, while blue (x) marks the control ones. During efferent activation, the frequency of the HBs under the artificial membrane converges to the stimulus frequency, in this case 40 Hz; the control HB increases in frequency but does not phase-lock to the stimulus.

FIGURE 5. (a) Step stimulus (150 μ A over 10 s) response for four representative HBs under the artificial membrane (red) and two control cells outside the membrane area (blue). The mica flake motion is presented in black at the top, and at the bottom the shape of the stimulus is depicted. The efferent stimulus was set in effect between the gray vertical dashed lines. (b) CC, bundle characteristic frequency, and motion amplitude, for all the cells in this experiment (gray) before, during, and after efferent stimulation. Highlighted in black (*) are CCs for the pairs of hair bundle traces with the artificial membrane position. Red (*) shows the characteristic frequency and amplitude for HBs coupled to the mica flake motion, while blue (x) marks the control ones.

An overall increase in the frequency of spontaneous oscillation was observed during the applied step current for all HBs, with a 60% increase of the global average across cells under the artificial membrane. However, the bundles that were strongly coupled to the artificial membrane showed a milder effect. Interestingly, control HBs exhibited a higher increase, with rates closer to 150%. Upon termination of the stimulus, these cells manifested a lingering effect, ending at a 10% increase in frequency with respect to the initial state. The amplitude of motion was reduced by efferents proportionally to the intensity of the current step, having similar decrease ratios among all cells. For the stimulus step of 150 μ A, shown in the figure, the amplitude decreased by approximately 30% during stimulation.

CONCLUSION

Activation of efferent neurons was shown to have a strong effect on systems of coupled hair bundles. We artificially coupled HCs of the sacculus of the American Bullfrog by introduction of mica flakes, which allowed us to track the active innate motility of coupled hair bundles. The innervating efferent neurons were stimulated electrically with either fixed-frequency pulse trains or continuous step stimuli. We observed that the coupled hair bundles were strongly affected by efferent activation, with the effects dependent on the specific stimulus waveform applied. Efferents was shown to play a role in shaping not only the amplitude and frequency of spontaneous oscillations, but also the degree of synchronization among cells coupled by the mica flake. Future work entails the application of mechanical stimuli to the artificial membrane while applying efferent activation, to study its effects on the sensitivity of the coupled system.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Robert, Fettiplace]:

This paper describes electrical stimulation of the efferent nerves on the spontaneous oscillation of the hair bundles of the frog saccular hair cells, demonstrating effects on the amplitude and frequency of the oscillations. Fig. 3 shows that the oscillation frequency is reduced during stimulation, converging to that of the efferent stimulus (5 Hz), suggesting the bundles are being driven by oscillations of hair cell membrane potential. A clever technique is to overlie the bundles with a thin mica plate to produce mechanical coupling, also shown to be susceptible to efferent stimulation. A weakness is relating to the results to the auditory efferents, stimulation of which desensitizes cochlear hair cells and nerve afferents (please refer to Fuchs & Lauer, 2019, which is the best general reference on efferents). In contrast, in vestibular cells, there are two types of efferent response an inhibition and an excitation (e.g., Brichta & Goldberg, 2000; Holt, Lysakowski & Goldberg 2006). The inhibition is produced by calcium influx through nicotinic ACh receptors triggering calcium activated (SK) K⁺ channels to generate diphasic or IPSPs; the excitation is produced by hair cells lacking the requisite SK channels, thus generating solely the cholinergic EPSPs. Is there any evidence that efferents to the saccular hair cells are solely inhibitory? The authors might refer to these in considering the mechanism, and clearly distinguish between auditory and vestibular effects. A small point is that throughout the noun ‘efferents’ should be used, not ‘efference’.

[Response - Martín, Toderi]: Thank you for your comments, Prof. Fettiplace. While electrophysiological recordings in the past have indeed shown that the efferent stimulus can, in a minority of cells, lead to excitatory effects, we have only observed an inhibitory role in our recordings. Specifically, prior experiments performed in our laboratory on individual cells of the bullfrog sacculus indicated that the effect of efferents is consistently inhibitory (Lin & Bozovic 2020, Lin & Bozovic 2022). We have added a brief discussion of this point to the manuscript.

[Jont, Allen]:

FM Radio, is trying to get a signal at 100 MHz and puts in a heterodyne signal to get to a base band to hear it. I would like to hear your comment on that, that the oscillations are heterodyning so they can be detected at base band. Is that a reasonable possibility? I am struck with the idea that these oscillations are doing the same thing.

[Response - Martín, Toderi]: I think that if they are not following the same frequency of the stimulus we are sending in every case, could be related to the fact that they have natural frequencies, relatively low, and so some follow and some do not. Sacculus does not have tonotopy but cells exhibit more sensitivity to particular frequencies. It is possible that the coupled system is acting as an ensemble with a resulting particular sensitivity that could be broke down by individual cells, when conveying this information.